

**IMPACT OF IN-SERVICE TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAMME OF
SARVA SHIKSHA ABHIYAN ON CLASSROOM PROCESSES AT
ELEMENTARY LEVEL.**

Smt. Amrita Majumder

Research Scholar, Dept. of Education, Vidyanagar, Mumbai-400098.

Dr. D. Harichandan

Faculty, IDOL, University of Mumbai, Vidyanagar, Mumbai-400098

Introduction:

Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, a flagship programme of Government of India for the promotion of Universalisation of Elementary Education has several features that seek to improve the quality of elementary education. The physical spaces of schools can be transformed into learning spaces only if certain basic provisioning is ensured. This provisioning includes an adequate number of teachers in schools, facilities for training of teachers, structures to provide regular on site academic support, grants to facilitate development of teaching learning material to aid classroom instruction, textbooks for children from special focus groups etc.

The teacher training programme places great emphasis on preparing the teachers for teaching by building their capacity through a series of training programmes. The SSA provides for regular 20 -days in-service training for every teacher every year along with facilities for 30 days training for newly recruited teachers and 60 days training for teachers those have not received pre-service training. Training covers several pedagogical issues including content and methodology, to improve teaching learning transactions at classroom level. States have started exploring several innovative means of imparting these trainings such as use of distance education, self learning mode and use of the educational technology.

Teacher training under SSA emphasizes, child-centered pedagogy and competency

based teaching learning. In 2006-07, about 29.5 lakh teachers underwent the annual in-service training. NCERT has prepared guidelines for in-service teacher training under SSA, called 'The Reflective Teacher' that advocates an optimum training duration of about 10 days per year. In-service training as suggested by NCERT, should be split up into institutional training 'on site' (that is, in the school), implementation of recommended strategies by the teachers in their own classroom settings

The present study, primarily aims at assessing the developmental perspective and different types of provisions of in-service teacher education programme under SarvaShikshaAbhiyan. To find out the impact of in-service teacher education programme on affective classroom processes by teachers and the impact of the same on student's performance. It will specifically examine how the recent education system has affected teachers understanding on matters covered in their training modules, how they are translating it in the classroom situation, how the follow up is being implemented as envisaged in the training module and what is its impact on classroom processes?

Research Aims:

The present study primarily aims at assessing the impact of in-service teacher education programme on effective classroom processes by teachers and the impact of the same on student's performance. It will specifically examine how the recent education system has affected teachers understanding on matters covered in their training modules, how they are translating it in the classroom situation, how the follow up is being implemented as envisaged in the training module and what is its impact on classroom processes.

Objectives:

- 1) To study the impact of in-service teacher education programme under Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan in terms of change in teacher's behavior.

- 2) To analysis the in-service teacher education programme under SarvaShikshaAbhiyan in terms of change in student's behavior
- 3) To assess the impact of in-service teacher education programme on Classroom processes under SarvaShikshaAbhiyan.

Research Questions:

The main purpose of the study is to examine the growth and development of SarvaShikshaAbhiyan and its impact on education, provision of in-service education programme under Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan and to access their changes in the teacher's and student's behavior for making them more effective. Hence, the following questions are formulated for the above objectives to study the problem.

- 1) How in-service teacher education programme under Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan can be more result oriented which could change the approach of teachers towards teaching processes in the class room.
- 2) How do elementary school students perceive about the quality of teachers who have under gone in-service teacher education programme under SarvaShikshaAbhiyan and the approaches of the students towards their trained teachers.
- 3) What are the impacts of in-service teacher education programme on classroomprocesses under SarvaShikshaAbhiyan and how it has shown the mark of improvement?

Scope and limitation of the Study

- 1) Only Brihanmumbai Municipal Corporation (BMC) schools under SarvaShikshaAbhiyan are included in the study.
- 2) The study conducted both in primary and upper primary schools under SarvaShikshaAbhiyan.
- 3) The study is limited to in-service teacher education course, not to pre-service and distance education.

- 4) The study is limited to Mumbai and suburb Mumbai not in other district of Maharashtra.
- 5) The study is limited to B.M.C Marathi; English and Hindi medium schools under SSA, other medium schools like Gujrati, Urdu, Telugu, and Kannad etc. are not included.

Methodology

A descriptive normative survey method has been used by researcher, it combines two research methods: gathering information to describe the object of the study (descriptive method) and critiquing of the object to identify ways to improve it (normative method).

Sample Size&Selections

Cluster sampling was used for carrying out the study. The sample size of the study is as given in tabular form.

1) Total Number of BMC Schools Selected

Marathi Medium	Hindi Medium	English Medium	Total No. of BMC Schools
13	09	08	30

2) In-service Teacher Trainers

Primary Section Teachers	Secondary Section Teachers	Total No. of Teachers
40	80	120

3) Focus Group Discussion

Classes	Boys	Girls	Total No of Students
3 rd & 4 th	23	20	43
5 th & 6 th	75	78	153
7 th & 8 th	81	73	154
Total	179	171	350

4) Classroom Observation

Trained Teachers	Un-trained Teachers	Total No. of Teachers
60	40	100

Sample selections

The researcher collected data from different elementary school teachers who received in-service training organized by SSA. The researcher selected clusters from different zone of Mumbai and suburbs i.e. Western, Central, and Harbourlines. Mumbai (ward A to E) has 234 BMC schools, Zone 1 has 339 BMC schools, Zone 3 has 715 BMC schools and Zone 4 has 513 BMC schools. The zone is divided into different Municipal Wards. Through random sampling methods, the researcher selected wards stretched from Mumbai to Dahisar (last suburb on Western Railway), Mulund (last suburb on Central Railway) and extended till Mankhurd (Harbour line).

Tools of Research

The researcher used tools developed by Sankar Prasad Mohanty, Ravenshaw University, Cuttack, Odisha (2013) for Elementary School Teachers, Focus Group Discussion (Students), and Classroom Observation Schedule to collect the data for the research study. Different tools were required to seek information regarding phenomena. Researcher used the following tools for collection of data:

- 1) Questionnaire for the Elementary School Teachers
- 2) Questionnaire for Guidelines for Focus Group Discussion
- 3) Questionnaire for Classroom Observation Schedule
- 4) Documentary Analysis.
- 5) Photographs.

Techniques of Data Analysis

The researcher collected data with the help of three tools to ascertain the quality on

in-service training programme for the elementary school teachers of Mumbai and suburb Mumbai.

The tools were used based on different dimensions in order to assess the quality of such training programme and the impact on classroom process as a result of such training. The data collected through the above tools; have been analyzed by using both quantitative and qualitative techniques. With permission from the Chairman of ward committee, Administer Officer (AO) of the ward, Head Masters (HM) of the concerned schools, the teachers were supplied the questionnaires to fill up at their convenience. Interviews were conducted with teachers available through an interview schedule to study the impact of in-service training programme on the classroom processes. During the visit, the classroom practices were also observed by the researcher with the help of classroom observation schedule.

The FGDs were organized during the school hour and in some cases during recreation period in a class room. The questions under the guidelines were based on the dimensions pertaining to the quality of in-service training for teachers and impact of such training as what they felt in the schools. The responses were recorded by the researcher.

The data collected from Classroom Observation Schedule (COS), to explore the impact of in-service training on classroom, were analyzed quantitatively by using percentage analysis technique and the significant differences between two percentages of the trained and untrained teachers were calculated.

Major Findings:

Perception of teachers on strengths of in-service training programme

Table 1 N=120

SI. No.	Strengths of in-service training	Numbers of teachers Expressed their views
1	Content Knowledge Enhancement	96.28 (80.24)

2	Sharing of Experiences	85.08 (70.90)
3	Interaction with other teachers	96.39 (80.33)
4	Knowledge of new methodology	84.22 (70.19)
5	Clear idea about spots	54 (45.00)
6	Innovative idea	84.12 (70.10)
7	Knowledge about new themes such as NCF, RTE Act etc	111.4(92.86)
8	Skills to present content sequentially	105.14(87.62)
9	School Beautification	73.71(61.43)
10	Maintenance of Statistical record	108 (90.00)

The figures in parenthesis represent percentage

From the Table 1, it was evident that in-service training enhanced their content knowledge as 80.24 % of trainees reported. Majority (92.86 %) of trainees expressed that knowledge pertaining to current themes such as NCF, RTE Act etc was imparted and it could help them in knowing new concepts. The training could enable them (80.33 %) to interact with each other regarding the problem they faced in the classrooms teaching and found solution of those problems through interaction. There was haring of experiences among teachers (70.90 %) out of teaching learning process in the school. Less number (45.00 %) of trainees reported that, the hard spots were addressed in the training programme. The hard spots of all the trainees could have been addressed during the training. There could be improvement of teaching strategies, methods among the teachers (trainees).

A. Major Weaknesses of the In-service Training Programme as perceived by Teachers

The teachers expressed, as presented in Table 2, about the major weaknesses of the in-service training programme the attended so far.

Table2
Perception of Teachers on Major Weaknesses of the In-Service Training Programme N=120

SI. No.	Weaknesses of In-Service Training:	Number of Teachers Expressed their views
1	Unwillingness of Teachers	39.43(32.86)
2	Lack of equipments	38.00(31.67)
3	Unsuitable dates for Training	78.51(65.43)
4	No substitution teacher arrangements	90.28(75.24)
5	No food arrangements	120(100.00)
6	No actual TA	120(100.00)
7	Uncomfortable sitting arrangements	108.27(90.23)
8	No Transportation arrangements	84 (70.00)
9	Unsuitable Training venue	48 (40.00)

The figures in parenthesis represents percentage

Table 2 depicts about the major weaknesses of in-service training programme as expressed by the teachers (trainees). Among all the weaknesses, lack of equipments and no proper sitting arrangements was reported by 90.00 % of teachers (31.67 and 90.00 respectively) chairs was uncomfortable , found uneasy to sit for long time writing facilities was not their ,no benches was arranged . Dates for training were not suitable, No substitution teacher were arranged for the schools, when teacher are on training no one to supervision classes in schools ,no transportation was provided, actual TA was not provided during the training as majority (>50.00 %) of teachers expressed their views on it.

1. It has noticed from the response of the in-service training teachers that more than twenty percent are facing difficult to attend training classes because of notice

given was too short, the venue of training place was long distance from their home and some other difficulties like lack of time, health problems etc. but more than thirty percent of the teachers felt there was no difficult in attending the training. Hence a significant number of respondents felt in-service training improve the teaching proficiency in the schools.

2. The response of the sample teachers infers that irrespective of their working area, more than sixty percent are attending the current training sessions but they felt the training dates are not suitable to them.

3. The sample teacher said there is no library/ reading room facility at the training centers.

4. The response of the teachers indicates that more than eighty percent of the trainees have received training materials during the training and they have read the material during the training period. A significant number of teachers did not read the training methods because of its difficult to understand and lack of time to read the material.

5. The analysis of data conclude with major deficiencies identified at training centres by the teachers are no internet facilities, television, DVD Player and type recorder, content was too theoretical .

6. A major group of in-service teachers felt the training programme was relevant to their needs because they felt lecture/ discussions, practical work, group discussions, self-study and guided study are most useful in the transaction methods used at training programme.

7. More than twenty percent of the sample teachers said that the reading and writing materials have given at training centres before the training period but they did not completed the reading and writing assignments as required by the training centre.

8. The opinions of the teachers on use of teaching aids shows good and excellent,

but in the participation of topic shows found average and below average.

9. It can be concluded that the interaction between trainees and resource persons found good and excellent and mastery over the subject shows good and excellent.

10. Eighty percent of the teachers felt the presentation of concepts is good and excellent; they are satisfied with opportunities given to trainees to seek clarification.

11. A significant number of teachers felt the training programme help them and enrich training understanding of the contents covered and they useful in learn things that they did not know before.

12. It can be concluded from the data that major group of teachers felt making it more interactive in the class and explaining some topics in a better way are learnt useful in improve the teaching. Whereas, giving more appropriate assignments and have works to children and testing students and using results for improvement of teaching are useful to some extent. Nearly forty percent of the respondents felt that paying attention to the children with learning difficulties in the class is most useful to improve teaching.

B. Analysis the In-Service Teacher Education Programme on Student's Behavior

Major outcomes of Discussion

Students expressed that the majority of the teachers ask questions related to the topic and courses of the study only. The teachers write the name of the topic and important points on the blackboard while teaching. Sometimes students are allowed to write on the blackboard as an activity based learning. Teachers follow participatory approach e.g. Question-answer, storytelling. Teachers rarely use Teaching Learning Materials even while teaching Math and Language, but they use it to some extent in teaching of Science and EVS.

The students are allowed to share their own experiences in the class for better learning; sometimes the students participate and feel free to give suggestion on the topic. Majority of the students reported that the teachers after in-service training

behave in friendly and respectful way .The trained teachers give desired answer with proper clarification on the questions asked by the students.

Majority of the students expressed that teachers uses pictures, models, charts, maps etc. for teaching. Teachers demonstrate certain activities such as group work, games, role play etc. to motivate / attract students towards learning different subjects. Electronic Teaching Materials such as Computer, TV, and Radio etc., are not used in the school. One computer is there but for office uses. Teachers after training create a suitable atmosphere and allow the students to participate in the class, so that they feel free to seek more information and elaboration on the topic taught by the teachers.

C. Classroom Observation Schedule:

1. It can be concluded that eighty percent of the classrooms were observed that the previous knowledge experience of the students was utilized, whereas, fifty percent of the un-trained teachers in the study area are not specialized in subject, which indicated the significant positive effect of in-service teacher training too on the skill of teacher.

2. More than seventy five percent of the classrooms in the study area are utilizing practical aids and observed that students are attending practical classes.

Less than fifty percent of the un-trained teachers have not shown teaching aids in time. Hence trained teacher differ significantly from their un-trained counterpart.

4. The study indicate that ninety percentage of trained and seventy five percentage of un-trained teachers use blackboard for teaching frequently .Hence trained and un-trained teachers did not differ significantly in the skill of blackboard use.

5. Most of the teachers found to be very careful while answering the questions asked by the students. Some time teachers found to postpone the answer of the questions raised by the students for the next day. Teachers receive feedback from the students about the method of teaching. It was also noticed that teachers

summarize the learning points at the end of the deliberations and was very active in delivering the lesson.

Conclusion:

It is undoubtedly true that the in-service teacher training under SSA constitute the cornerstone of the entire education system in Mumbai. The teachers need the proper platform where they could get latest information mainly about the latest teaching techniques and strategies. The modern methods and approaches to interact with the students effectively being devised by various scholars of modern time should be brought down to the level of the teachers associated with upper primary education. As many as the teachers opined that there is no difficult in training, but a significant number felt the commence period was very short and the location of training programme was long distance from their working place.

The training component has been judged useful for teachers to a large extent in the areas of; use of Teaching Learning Material in classroom situation, activity based teaching and child centered approach followed by subject enrichment. Training material was made available to 98 % trainees /participants as and when the training programmes were organized.

The Resource Persons stressed mainly on discussion approach and demonstration techniques while communicating with the trainees. Usefulness of resource material in the actual classroom situation is not as effective as it should have been.

Majority of the teachers serving at primary level in the selected schools are not possessing higher academic qualifications. However most of them possess the desired professional educational qualifications.

Suggestions:

- Teaching Learning Materials were not used frequently.
- Modern ICT tools like computers with internet connectivity, LCD projectors should be used for presentation of information which may bring more clarity and understanding among the trainees.

- The teachers (trainees) suggested that, in-service training for the elementary school teachers needs to be compulsory for all untrained teachers.
- Proper pause, intonation, pronunciation etc. were lacking while reading a loud by the teachers.
- Food arrangements, sitting arrangements, suitable date for the training should be provide in training centre.

References:

- Aggarwal, V.P and Kamalesaro, G. (1997). *The Quality of In-Service Teacher Programme for Primary School Teachers An Appraisal Study*. New Delhi: NCERT.
- Aiholli, V.D. and Sahoo, K. (1995). *Nature and forms of In-Service Education for Secondary School Teachers in the Karnataka State by 2005 A.D* Vol.31 No.3.
- Chauhan, D.R.R, Sharma, B. &Rawat, J. (2009). *In-service teacher training programme under SSA in (Sunni) educational block of district Shimla: an evaluative study*. Retrieved from [http://hp.gov.in/SSA/page/~/_/test/file.axd?file=09 % f5.pdf](http://hp.gov.in/SSA/page/~/_/test/file.axd?file=09%20%20f5.pdf). dated 28.12.2011.
- Das, Amarendra.(2007). *How Far Have We Come in SarvaSikshaAbhiyan?* Economic and Political Weekly. January 06, Vol-XLII No.01
- Dilshad, R.M.(2010). Assessing quality of teacher education: a student perspective, Pakistan. *Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)* 30, (1), pp. 85-97.
- Gopalan, K.(2003). Some quality issues in teacher education. *University News*, 41 (07), pp.1-3
- Gupta, A.K. (1984). *Teacher Education: Current Status and Prospects*. New Delhi: Sterling Publications.

- Kulkarni, V.G. (1997). *An Investigation into the Classroom Management Behaviours of Teacher and its implication for the Teacher Training*. Ph.D. Education, Shivaji University.
- Mishra & Kishore. (1997). *Teacher Empowerment Issues Related to Development of local specific competencies based curriculum at Primary level* New Delhi: NCERT.
- National Council for Teacher Education (2009). *National Curriculum framework for teacher education*. New Delhi: NCTE.
- Paranjpe and Sandhya. (1997). *Developing Partnership for Teacher Empowerment: A focus on INSET*. New Delhi
- Prahallada, N.N. (2003). Teacher orientation, enrichment and up graduation. *Edutracks*, 2 (5), 22-25.
- Prasad & Prasad. (2005, May). *Towards Professionalization in Education*. *University News*, Vol.43 No. 18. New Delhi.
- Rao, Nitya (2009). *Structural Constraints in Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan Schools*. *Economic and Political Weekly*. April 18, Vol. XLIV No. 16.
- Singh Kainth, Gursharan. (2006). *A Mission Approach to Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan*. *Economic and Political Weekly*. July 29, Vol-XLI No.30
- Vijayakumar, B. (2005). *A study on teachers training under SSA*. Thiruvananthapuram: State Resource Center. Retrived from http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/1546/18/18_chapter%202.pdf
- Yadav.S.K. (2012). *SSA INSET Packages in states: An Assessment*. New Delhi: NCERT.